

Deleuze, reader of Blanchot – On the immortality of death in and as cinema

Deleuze, lector de Blanchot – Sobre la inmortalidad de la muerte en y como cine

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Diogo Emanuel da Nóbrega e Silva

Universidade NOVA de Lisboa – School of Social Sciences and Humanities

diogonobrega15@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT: This article explores Deleuze's notion of death, focusing on the advances made on the basis of Blanchot's 'double death' (*mort double*). I begin with the following hypothesis: Deleuze is interested not exactly in death but in dying, not in life's length, but rather the interminable event that comes without ever arriving. My argument unfolds in two stages. First, I establish the philosophical background of Deleuze's work on this question, namely Blanchot's conception of impersonal death as a reversal of the possible into the impossible, of the 'I die' into the 'They die', they do not cease, and they do not finish dying. Second, through Deleuze's analysis of Samuel Beckett's *Film*, we will see that this impossibility signifies the movement that cinema essentially is, that is, the endless exhaustion, involution, of the onto-theo-logical place of the self, its interminable death. In this sense, we will see that Lazarus becomes *the* character of cinema, not the Lazarus of the Gospels, a character in a miraculous story, who recovers from death, but other Lazarus, Blanchot's Lazarus, 'whose very death was resurrected'.

Keywords: Deleuze, Blanchot, dying, cinema, Beckett

RESUMEN: Este artículo explora la noción de muerte de Deleuze, centrándose en los avances realizados a partir de la 'doble muerte' (*mort double*) de Blanchot. Partimos de la siguiente hipótesis: Deleuze se interesa no exactamente por la muerte sino por el morir, no por la duración de la vida, sino por el acontecimiento interminable que llega sin llegar nunca. El argumento se desarrolla en dos etapas: en primer lugar, estableceremos el trasfondo filosófico del trabajo de Deleuze sobre esta cuestión, a saber, el pensamiento de Blanchot sobre la muerte impersonal como inversión de lo posible en lo imposible, del 'yo muero' en el 'se muere', no se deja ni se termina de morir. En segundo lugar, a través del análisis de Deleuze sobre «Film», de Samuel Beckett, veremos que esta imposibilidad significa el movimiento que el cine esencialmente es, es decir, el agotamiento sin fin, la involución, del lugar onto-teo-lógico del 'yo', su muerte interminable. En este sentido, veremos que Lázaro se convierte en 'el' personaje del cine, no el Lázaro de los Evangelios, el personaje de una historia milagrosa, que se recupera de la muerte, sino otro Lázaro, el Lázaro de Blanchot, 'cuya propia muerte fue resucitada'.

Palabras clave: Deleuze, Blanchot, morir, cine, Beckett

Introduction

The importance of the concept of ‘death’¹ in Deleuze’s philosophical work generally raises two distinct interpretative perspectives: either it is a concept of no fundamental relevance in a philosophy primarily concerned with «transformation», and thus functioning, to use Jean-Luc Nancy’s expression, “in a universe without death”,² or it is the leading motif of Deleuze’s *oeuvre*, as Alain Badiou famously asserts in *Deleuze - La Clameur de L’être*³. As Badiou writes:

One should not be misled by the use of the word ‘anarchy’ to designate the nomadism of singularities, for Deleuze specifies ‘crowned anarchy’, and it is crucial to think also –indeed, to think above all – of the crown. This is attributed to beings who have ascetically renounced the ‘lived experiences’ and ‘states of affairs’ that constituted their sentimental, intellectual, or social actuality and who have had the power (*puissance*) to exceed their limits, to go ‘where they are borne by hubris’ (*là où l’hybris les porte*).

¹ I am not trying to suggest that there is a single, unified concept of death in Deleuze’s work. After all, in Deleuze there’s no unified concept at all: “Every concept is at least double or triple, etc.” Deleuze, Gilles, *Qu’est-ce que la philosophie* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit), p. 21. Deleuze revisits the problem of death multiple times, namely in *Presentation De Sacher-Masoch, Différence et répétition, Logique du Sens* or *L’Anti-Œdipe*, in the context of his long *auseinandersetzung* with Freud, particularly with Freud’s reduction of death to “the qualitative and quantitative return of the living to inanimate matter.” Deleuze, Gilles, *Différence et répétition* (Paris: Presses universitaires de France), p. 145. Deleuze aspires to a non-objective model of death. As Pierre Montebello rightly observes, “To desire death is not at all to desire a return to matter. It is not at all funereal. (...) To desire death is not to desire to die materially. This is only the death of the I, the dying I (*le Je meurs*) that can no doubt be represented in the return to inanimate matter. In reading Blanchot (*L’espace littéraire*), Deleuze discovers that there is a more powerful death, the anonymous death that passes through the living I (*la mort anonyme qui traverse le Je vivant*) (...)” Montebello, Pierre, “L’instinct de mort chez Deleuze. La controverse avec la psychanalyse”. *DoisPontos*, vol. 8, n. 2, (2011), p.18. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5380/dp.v8i2.21932>. It is precisely this anonymous, impersonal death, which Deleuze discovered when ‘reading Blanchot’ (*en lisant Blanchot*), that we will consider here. For further context on Deleuze’s reworking of Freud’s *Todstrieb* see Pearson, Keith Ansell, *Germinal life: The difference and repetition of Deleuze* (London: Routledge, 1999), pp. 104-114; see also Adkins, Brent, *Death and desire in Hegel, Heidegger and Deleuze* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2007); see also Leites, Bruno. “Deleuze and the Work of Death: A Study from the Impulse-Images”. *Deleuze and Guattari Studies*, 14(2), (2020), 229–254. doi:10.3366/dlgs.2020.0400.

² Nancy, Jean-Luc, *Le Différence Parallele* (Verona: Ombre Corte, 2008), p. 25.

³ This is a hypothesis that is partly followed by Peter Hallward: “What is really at stake in Deleuze’s work, therefore, is not some sort of enhanced creatural mobility, a set of techniques that might enable more supple or more fruitful modes of actual interaction. What matters is instead the redemptive re-orientation of any particular creature towards its own dissolution. (...) Deleuze is most appropriately read as a spiritual, redemptive or subtractive thinker, a thinker preoccupied with the mechanics of dis-embodiment and de-materialization.” Hallward, Peter, *Out of this World – Deleuze and the Philosophy of Creation* (London: Verso, 2006), p. 3. For Deleuze, however, as he states in *Cinéma 1*, «subtraction» is what defines subjectivity. On his view, the subjective subtracts whatever is of no interest to it; subtraction is an inevitable consequence of making choices. What interests Deleuze, as we shall see, is not subtraction but exhaustion. Exhausting is the opposite of subtracting: it does not choose but exhausts the possible, including the exhaustion of subjectivity itself.

The result is that this philosophy of life is essentially, just like Stoicism (but not at all like Spinozism, despite the reverence in which Deleuze holds Spinoza), a philosophy of death (*une philosophie de la mort*).⁴

To Badiou, ‘hubris’ in the Deleuzian sense corresponds to an ascetic renunciation of ‘lived experiences’, of the ‘state of affairs’. This renunciation, he adds, must be of a definitive nature: one must definitively renounce. As he explains, “thought [as Deleuze would have it] exists as the fracturing of my actuality and the dissipation of my limit.”⁵ In this way, Badiou infers, “the metaphor for the event of thought is dying (...) for thinking consists precisely in ascetically attaining that point where the individual is transfixed by the impersonal exteriority that is equally his or her authentic being.”⁶ At the heart of Deleuze’s work, Badiou suggests, thinking comprehends a progressive element; it’s necessary to progress subtractively, overcoming a series of identifiable stations, ‘fracture’, ‘ascesis’, ‘dissipation’, back to the precise point where the individual abandons his factic limits, reuniting with ‘his authentic being’ (*son être authentique*). To think, to begin to think, ultimately corresponds to ceasing to be, to exist: “This identity of thinking and dying is declared in a veritable hymn to death (...).”⁷

I will not dwell excessively on Badiou’s hermeneutic hypothesis but will merely express some reservations regarding his interpretation. To support his reading, for example, Badiou quotes a passage from *Logique du Sens*:

Deleuze, slipping effortlessly into the footsteps of Blanchot, exalts ‘the point at which ... the impersonality of dying no longer indicates only the moment when I disappear outside of myself, but rather the moment when death loses itself in itself, and also the figure which the most singular life takes on in order to substitute itself for me’.⁸

In its full context, however, the passage from Deleuze’s text reads as follows:

It is at this mobile and precise point (*C’est au point mobile et précis*), where all events gather together in one that transmutation happens: this is the point at which death turns against death; where dying is the destitution of death (*où le mourir est comme la destitution de la mort*), and the impersonality

⁴ Badiou, Alan, *Deleuze – La Clameur de l’Être* (Paris: Fayard/ Pluriel, 2013), pp. 23-24.

⁵ Badiou, *Deleuze – La Clameur de l’Être*, p. 24.

⁶ Badiou, *Deleuze – La Clameur de l’Être*, p. 24.

⁷ Badiou, *Deleuze – La Clameur de l’Être*, p. 24.

⁸ Badiou, *Deleuze – La Clameur de l’Être*, p. 24.

of dying (*l'impersonnalité du mourir*) no longer indicates only the moment when I disappear outside of myself, but rather the moment when death loses itself in itself, and also the figure which the most singular life takes on in order to substitute itself for me.⁹

The vast ellipse on which Badiou relies, the suspension points that separate the expressions ‘the point at which’ and ‘the impersonality of dying’, hide the nature of the ‘point’ that Deleuze wants us to consider. It is a ‘mobile and precise point’, which means that we cannot proceed towards it. It does not have the solidity that would sustain such a relation. It is not a term but rather the interminable: it ‘happens’, i.e., it takes place only once, and always anew, each time only one time. This double aspect of the ‘point’, its ‘mobility’ and ‘precision’, is adequate to the eternal return. In the closing remarks of the *VII colloque philosophique international de Royaumont*, dedicated to Nietzsche, Deleuze talks about the eternal return in terms of ‘continuity’ and ‘iteration’.¹⁰

According to the Ernout-Meillet dictionary, the Latin adverb *iterum* means “for the second time (*pour la deuxième fois*)”¹¹ or, as the lexicographer Giovanni Semerano suggests, “once again (*ancora una volta*).”¹² The word comes from the Sanskrit *ítarah*, ‘other’. As the continuity of an iterative movement eternal return must therefore be read in terms of the essential connection between repetition and alterity: not the mechanical repetition of the Same, the Identical,¹³ but of the ‘other’, the ‘new’. The ‘point’ to which Deleuze refers does not exist, as Badiou seems to claim, at the end of a linear itinerary, of an apocalyptic graduality, but as the persistence of an event that each time repeats for the first time. Hence the description that Deleuze provides and that Badiou’s ellipses strategically conceal, ‘not only the moment when I disappear outside of myself’, but rather ‘the point at which death turns against death’, i.e., ‘where dying is the destitution of death’, deferring it indefinitely.¹⁴

⁹ Deleuze, Gilles, *Logique du Sens* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1969), p. 179.

¹⁰ See Gilles Deleuze, “Conclusions – sur la volonté de puissance et l'éternel retour”. In *Cahiers de Royaumont. Nietzsche*, pp. 275-288. Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1966.

¹¹ Ernout, Alfred; Meillet, Alfred, *Dictionnaire Étymologique de la Langue Latine* (Paris: Klincksieck, 1985), p. 325.

¹² Semerano, Giovanni, *Le Origini della Cultura Europea, Vol. II – Dizionario Etimologici, Basi semitiche delle lingue indeuropee – Dizionario della Lingua Latina e di Voci Moderne* (Firenze: Leo S. Olschki Editore, 1994), p. 439.

¹³ “Nietzsche meant nothing more than this by eternal return. Eternal return cannot mean the return of the Identical because it presupposes a world (that of the will to power) in which all previous identities have been abolished and dissolved. Returning is being, but only the being of becoming.” Deleuze, *Différence et répétition*, p. 59.

¹⁴ In *Mille Plateaux*, for example, Deleuze tells us that Oedipus “invents something worse than death”, i.e., “unlimited postponement (*atermoiement illimité*).” Deleuze, Gilles, Guattari, Felix, *Mille Plateaux – Capitalisme et Schizophrénie 2* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1980), p. 156. «Worse», in this context, means, in Nietzsche’s words, “without the privilege of the dead (*dem Vorrecht der Todten*)”, i.e., “no longer to die (*Nicht mehr zu*

The hypothesis I wish to corroborate is that Deleuze's problem is not 'death' but 'dying', the persistence of 'dying' as the condition of the new, beyond any kind of definitively ascribable ground or foundation – as in Paul's assertion, "every day I die (καθ' ἡμέραν ἀποθνῄσκω)" (1 Cor. 15, 31).¹⁵ An 'I', a Self, an identity that dies every day, this is the leading motif of Deleuze's philosophical work.

Contrary to Badiou's thanatological hypothesis, Jean-Luc Nancy reproduce the most common point of view among Deleuze's commentators, by understanding Deleuze's work as offering a vitalist and affirmative conception of the world, one that is rigorously focused on the problem of perennial 'transformation' and therefore immune to any form of negativity:

(...) this is exactly the question of negativity because birth and death point to something emerging from nothing and vanishing into nothingness – *ex nihilo and in nihilum*. It is a question that transformation does not pose. Consequently, if one takes transformation seriously, one must make it work on this side of birth and on the other side of death. This means that, in effect, the universe of transformation is a universe without negativity and thus a universe without death and without evil, at least without positive evil, like Spinoza's universe and in any case Deleuze's universe.¹⁶

'A universe without death and without evil', 'without negativity', i.e., entirely hostage to a transformative continuity that knows no disruption.¹⁷ With Roberto Esposito, I would argue that "one should not believe that he [Deleuze] undervalues the problem of the negative"; on the contrary, "one could say that his entire oeuvre is obsessed with it – on the one hand engaged in erasing it, on the other always exposed to its return."¹⁸ Deleuze's philosophy does not simply, or naively, ignore the problem of negativity, but rather entirely revolves, to use a word from Benjamin Noys, around its 'persistence'.¹⁹ Negativity has classically been determined by dialectics, that is to say, by

sterben)." Nietzsche, Friedrich, *Sämtliche Werke Band 3 – Morgenröte. Idyllen aus Messina. Die Fröhliche Wissenschaft* (Berlin: De Gruyter, 1999), p. 518.

¹⁵ *Novum Testamentum Graece*, Begründet von Heberhard und Erwin Nestle, Herausgegeben von Barbara und Kurt Aland, Joannes Karavidopolous, Carlo M. Martini, Bruce M. Metzger (Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2012), p. 550.

¹⁶ Nancy, Jean-Luc, *Le Différence Parallele* (Verona: Ombre Corte, 2008), p. 25.

¹⁷ The problem with Nancy's interpretation, as with Badiou's, is that it presupposes a concept of death as a definitive and objective occurrence, thus missing the revitalization of death that Deleuze is trying to achieve, that is, as something that "occurs in life and for life, in every passage or becoming, in every intensity as passage or becoming (*dans toute intensité comme passage et devenir*)." Deleuze, Gilles, Guattari, Felix, *L'Anti-Œdipe - Capitalisme et schizophrénie* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1972), p. 394.

¹⁸ Esposito, Roberto, *Pensiero Istituyente, Tre paradigmi di Ontologia Politica* (Torino: Einaudi, 2020), p. 88.

¹⁹ According to Noys we should consider an "image of Deleuze as internally fissured along the axis of negativity, (...) a continuing struggle within Deleuze's work with the effects of negativity." Noys, Benjamin, *The Persistence*

metaphysics, as *work* in the service of the constitution of meaning.²⁰ Deleuze is otherwise interested in indefinitely deferring any such possibility, the pleroma of negativity: “the outcome is no longer (...) sudden death but survival under reprieve, unlimited postponement (*une survivance en sursis, un attermoiement illimité*).”²¹

1. Impersonal death

Deleuze’s conception of ‘death’ draws explicitly on the work of Maurice Blanchot: “Blanchot rightly suggests that death has two aspects. One is personal, concerning the I or the ego”, and the other “is strangely impersonal, with no relation to «me», neither present nor past but always coming (...).”²² The idea that death is the place of an essential *dédoublement* is indeed a central motif along Blanchot literary and philosophical writings. There is empirical death, which concerns the “I” and which is always in a present “where I would die in the affirmation of my own reality and my unique existence (*de ma réalité propre et de mon existence unique*).”²³ And there is impersonal death, the death of “one” (*on*), or ‘the death of nobody’ (*la mort de personne*), above all not the ipseic death proper to me. “It is the abyss of the present”, Blanchot observes, “the time without present with which I have no relation, myself, that toward which I cannot go forth, for in it I do not die, I have fallen from the power to die. In it they die (*on meurt*), they do not cease, and they do not finish dying (*on ne cesse pas et on n’en finit pas de mourir*).”²⁴

To understand this double death, or better still, this doubleness within death, we must follow Blanchot’s reading of Rilke. As Blanchot suggests, in the early stages of his poetic career, Rilke “lived intensely this need to link the word death with the word authenticity.” The collection entitled *Das Stunden-Buch*, first published in 1905, gives us, what is perhaps, the most famous example of this: “Oh Lord, give to each his own (*eignen*) death.”²⁵ At the heart of the poet’s prayer lies the anguish

of the Negative, A Critique of Contemporary Continental Theory (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2010), p. 56.

²⁰ Curiously enough Nancy detects at the core of Hegel’s work the ‘restlessness of the Negative’, which is the principle of its own auto-deconstruction at the core of dialectics. He does not find this principle in Deleuze, in its universe resolutely beyond any effect of negativity. See Nancy, Jean-Luc, *Hegel, l’inquiétude du négatif* (Paris: Galilée, 2002).

²¹ Deleuze, *Mille Plateaux*, p. 156.

²² Deleuze, *Différence et répétition*, p. 148. See also *Logique du Sens*, p. 178ff ; and *L’Anti-Œdipe*, p. 394ff.

²³ Blanchot, Maurice, *L’Espace Littéraire* (Paris: Gallimard, 1955), p. 154.

²⁴ Blanchot, Maurice, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 160.

²⁵ Rilke, Rainer Maria, *Das Stunden-buch*. (Berlin: Verlag, 1955), p. 93.

of an anonymous death, of a generic ‘they die’, as well as the hope for a clear-sighted being-towards the possibility which is absolutely proper to me, and only to me, the hope for an ‘I die’. It is properness or authenticity, Rilke reflects further, of which the men from the ‘great cities’ (*großen Städte*) are deprived: “abased (*entwürdigen*) by the fatiguing labor / of serving without spirit senseless things (...) <they> wander in solitude around the hospitals, / waiting, terrified, the day of admission,” that is “the little death (*der kleine tod*) they finally grasp in there, / their own death hangs in them like a sour, green fruit, which doesn’t ripen (*die nicht reift*).”²⁶ The death to which the poet aspires is something other than an accident that arrives from the outside to terminate us hastily, than “a foreign death,” in Blanchot’s words, “that makes us die in the distress of estrangement.”²⁷ Rather, it is the final achievement of great patience, a task carefully done: “it was a death which good work had profoundly formed, this proper death which has so great a need of us because we live it, and to which we are never nearer than here.”²⁸ The image of a long maturation suggests the idea of an unhurried effort,²⁹ where one’s relation to time is profoundly transformed, as is one’s relation with one’s will, which calculates and projects.³⁰ The precise content of this unhurried effort, however, remains unclear: “This patience”, Blanchot writes, “though it separates us from all forms of daily activity, is not inactive. But its procedure is mysterious,”³¹ referring only to its own secret.

What interest us here, beyond further scrutiny of the specific content of the ‘patience’ described by Rilke, is the horizon of ‘meaning’ that finally fulfills its movement: at the end of a long maturation, a ‘proper’, ‘authentic’ death “that comes forth from that life in which we had love, distress and

²⁶ Rilke, *Das Stunden-buch*, p. 93. In *Orpheus. Eurydice. Hermes.*, Rilke invites us to consider a different image, a different fruit: “Like a fruit ripe with sweetness and night she was filled with her great death (*Wie eine Frucht von Süßigkeit und Dunkel, so war sie voll von ihrem großen Tode*) (...).” Rilke, Rainer Maria, *Neue Gedichte* (Frankfurt am Main: Insel Verlag, 1975), pp. 69-70.

²⁷ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 128.

²⁸ Rilke cited by Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 128.

²⁹ We are not far from the Platonic motif of μελέτη θανάτου (*Phaedo* 81a), not just a ‘meditation on death’ but a ‘practice’, a preparatory exercise. The verb μέλω means ‘to be an object of care’ or ‘thought’, or in an active sense, to ‘care for’, ‘take an interest in’; μελέτη means ‘care’, ‘attention’, a careful and considerate exercise, an occupation that is a preoccupation. Anticipating it thoughtfully, Rilke is always on the eve of death, ceaselessly watching over it.

³⁰ Note the following passage from Heidegger’s *Parmenides*: “Rilke takes over the form [to firmly distance himself from it, *bien entendu*] of this determination that arose in the modern age and was solidified in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries: from the Greek ζῷον λόγος ἔχων to the *animal rationale*. (...) As *animal rationale* man is the «animal» that calculates, plans (*das rechnende, planende*) turns to beings as objects, represents what is objective and orders it (...) This implies that man himself is the ‘subject’, the being that, positing itself on itself, disposes of its objects and in that way secures them for itself.” Heidegger, Martin, *Gesamtausgabe Band 54 – Parmenides* (Frankfurt: Vittorio Klostermann, 1992), pp. 231-232.

³¹ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 129.

meaning (*das aus jenem Leben geht, darin er Liebe hatte, Sinn und Not*).³² According to Blanchot, this search for a «proper» death “is rooted in a form of individualism which belongs to the end of the nineteenth century and which was endowed with its noble pride by a narrowly interpreted Nietzsche. Nietzsche too wishes to die his own death (*mourir de sa morte*). Hence the excellence he sees in voluntary death.”³³ We can find the Nietzsche to which Blanchot refers in the following passage from *Also sprach Zarathustra*: “My death I praise to you (*Meinen Tod lobe ich euch*), the free death that comes to me because I want (*weil ich will*).”³⁴ This mineness of death is thus entirely adequate to an ‘I’ that ‘wants’, that sovereignly decides to suspend its historical itinerary on its own terms: as Zarathustra urges, “die at the right time (*stirb zur rechten Zeit*).”³⁵ This is a question of dating death, of abolishing the future as the secret of an indecipherable death: through free, voluntary death, as Blanchot explains, “I want to kill myself at a determined moment. I link death to now: yes, now, now. But nothing better indicates the illusion, the madness of this ‘I want’, for death is never present (*la mort n’est jamais présent*).”³⁶

For Blanchot death is without present, without possibility. As Etienne Pinat rightly observes, the impossibility of death “is at the heart of Blanchot's work (...) and constitutes its profound originality (...)”³⁷ Note, by way of example the following lines from *Thomas l’obscur* and from *L’Instant de ma mort*: “In death itself, he was deprived of death (*dans la mort même, privé de la mort*);³⁸ “prevented from dying by death itself (*empêché de mourir par la mort même*).”³⁹ What does this mean, exactly? It means that it is impossible to experience death in the first person, to have an experience of death, to know it, and therefore to have death as knowledge: “we see ourselves, rather, as condemned, in death itself, to the impossibility of dying (*à l’impossibilité de mourir*).”⁴⁰ This is an established motif in the philosophical tradition. As Epicurus famously put it: “(...) when we are, death is not come, and, when death is come, we are not (ὅταν δὲ ὁ θάνατος παρῆ, τόθ’ ἡμεῖς οὐκ ἔσμεν).”⁴¹ This

³² Rilke, *Das Stunden-buch*, p. 93.

³³ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 123.

³⁴ Nietzsche, Friedrich, *Sämtliche Werke Band 4 – Also sprach Zarathustra I–IV* (Berlin: De Gruyter, 1988), p. 94.

³⁵ Nietzsche, *Sämtliche Werke Band 4 – Also sprach Zarathustra I–IV*, p. 93.

³⁶ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 103.

³⁷ Pinat, Etienne, *Les deux morts de Maurice Blanchot. Une Phénoménologie* (Bucarest: Zeta books, 2014), p. 35.

³⁸ Blanchot, Maurice, *Thomas l’obscur* (Paris: Gallimard, 1950), p. 40.

³⁹ Blanchot, Maurice, *L’instant de ma mort* (Paris: Gallimard, 2002), p. 9.

⁴⁰ Blanchot, Maurice, *La Part du feu* (Paris: Gallimard, 1984), p. 246.

⁴¹ P. von der Mühl, *Epicuri epistulae tris et ratae sententiae a Laertio Diogene servatae*, Leipzig: Teubner, 1922: 44-50. Retrieved from: <http://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/Iris/Cite?0537:008:1342>

observation is equally central to Heidegger's philosophical project: "(...) *Dasein* doesn't die – doesn't die properly (*nicht eigentlich stirbt*) – in and by the Experience of its factual demising."⁴² Blanchot develops this notion further, arguing that it is a matter of underlining not only the impossibility of living death, but the 'impossibility of dying':

As long as I live, I am a mortal man, but when I die, by ceasing to be a man I also cease to be mortal, I am no longer capable of dying, and my impending death horrifies me because I see it as it is: no longer death but the impossibility of dying (*non plus mort, mais impossibilité de mourir*).⁴³

'No longer death', writes Blanchot, 'but impossibility of dying', an impossibility that is not related to and cannot be clarified by a biology or psychology of death. In a psychology of death, as a characterization of the conditions under which a demise is 'experienced' and of the ways in which it is 'experienced', the concept of death is already presupposed, allowing us to gather information about the living of the 'person' who is dying and not about death itself. Blanchot's 'impossibility of dying' is not an ego-logical problem; it has nothing to do with the experience of a particular person but precisely with death itself, "the death without any name", as it reads in *L'Écriture du Désastre*, "the death outside the concept, *impossibility* itself (*l'impossibilité même*)."⁴⁴ Death as a possibility for man ends with man himself. The demise of man, his disappearance, is the disappearance of death, its impossibilization: "the impossible death", as Etienne Pinat writes, means that "losing life is essentially losing death (*perdre la vie, c'est essentiellement perdre la mort*). What makes death impossible is that it ceases to be possible when it becomes effective, when it is realized."⁴⁵ From the moment it becomes effective, death ends all possibilities, and thus its own possibility. It is not enough therefore to affirm with Epicurus that 'when death is come, we are not', because death cannot come; it is without present, it cannot be reconciled with possibility: "in death the possibility which is death dies too."⁴⁶ Hence the suggestion in *L'Instant de ma mort* I previously referred, i.e., that man is 'prevented from dying by death itself', and that he who dies finds only the impossibility of dying.

Blanchot is not saying that we are not mortals, that the impossibility of dying implies the immortality of man. It is precisely insofar as he is mortal that man cannot die: "through death I lose the advantage

⁴² Heidegger, Martin, *Gesamtausgabe Band 2 – Sein und Zeit* (Frankfurt: Vittorio Klostermann, 1977), p. 329.

⁴³ Blanchot, *La Part du feu*, p. 325.

⁴⁴ Blanchot, Maurice, *L'Écriture du Désastre*. (Paris: Gallimard, 1980), p. 112.

⁴⁵ Pinat, *Les deux morts de Maurice Blanchot*, p. 37.

⁴⁶ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 274.

of being mortal.”⁴⁷ The impossibility of dying therefore implies the immortality not of man but of death itself, its iterative resurrection: “He walked, the only true Lazarus, whose very death was resurrected (*dont la mort même était ressuscitée*).”⁴⁸ The challenge of this resurrection as nothing to do with any kind of return to life, i.e., to a life that is carefully and clearly separated from the death that suspend it; rather it concerns the ontological belonging-together of ‘life death’⁴⁹.

To understand this, we must ask ourselves how Lazarus walks, at what pace, what rhythm? Blanchot’s Lazarus is consubstantial to a *pas au-delà*. Note that the French ‘pas’ is a polysemic term. As an adverb of negation ‘pas’ means ‘not’; as a noun, however, it means ‘step’, ‘pace’, it designates walking, marching, in a word, locomotion. The walking that we are trying to grasp here preserves this dual idea of a paralysis, the disruption of a step and of a not beyond, *pas au-delà*.⁵⁰ This was emphasized by Jean-Luc Nancy in his comments on *Blanchot's Resurrection*: “the true Lazarus lives his dying as he dies his living. So it is that he ‘walks»’.”⁵¹ A certain step/ not beyond determines the ontological substance of a being “snatched at once from death and from life”, that is, whose walk affirms their simultaneity: “he walked passing beyond the last shadows of night (...) walking at a regular pace (*d’un pas égal*) beneath the falling stars, the same pace which for those men who are not wrapped in a shroud, marks the ascent toward the most precious point in life,”⁵² i.e., where life can

⁴⁷ Blanchot, *La Part du feu*, p. 325.

⁴⁸ Blanchot, *Thomas l’obscur*, p. 42.

⁴⁹ ‘Life death’, *La vie la mort*, as is well known, is a Derridean notion: “(...) with the blank of a pause or the invisible mark of a beyond, ‘life death’ (*la vie la mort*), I am neither opposing nor identifying life and death (neither and [e] nor is [esf]), I am neutralizing, as it were, both opposition and identification (...)” Derrida, Jacques, *La vie la mort (Séminaire 1975-1976)* (Paris: Seuil, 2019), p. 25. Philosophical intuition, if we understand it, already at work in Heidegger: “For those who are stubborn [*eigensinnig*, ‘stubborn’, ‘obstinate’, ‘him who has only one idea in his head’] life is merely life. Death is death and only that (*Tod ist ihnen Tod und nur dieses*). (...) But the Being of life”, writes Heidegger “is at once death (*ist zugleich Tod*).” The decisive element is precisely the simultaneity of life death, ‘at once’, ‘at the same time’, *zugleich*, as we read, ‘simultaneously’ life death. Heidegger, Martin, *Gesamtausgabe Band 40 – Einführung in die Metaphysik* (Frankfurt: Vittorio Klostermann, 1983), p. 140.

⁵⁰ See Blanchot, Maurice, *Le pas au-delà* (Paris: Gallimard, 1973). “What counts in the final accounting and beyond what can be counted,” writes Derrida, “is a certain step/ not beyond. I am thinking here of Maurice Blanchot’s syntaxless syntax in his *Pas au-dela*. There, he approaches death in what I would call a step-by-step procedure of overstepping or of impossible transgression (*une dé-marche de franchissement ou de transgression impossible*). *Ecce Homo*: ‘In order to understand anything at all of my Zarathustra, one must perhaps be similarly conditioned as I am – with one foot beyond life.’ A foot, and going beyond the opposition between life and/or death, a single step.” Derrida, Jacques, *Otobiographies* (Paris: Galilée, 2005), p. 69. For a detailed analysis of the term ‘pas’ in Blanchot’s *oeuvre*, see also Derrida, Jacques, *Parages* (Paris: Galilée, 2003), pp. 19-116.

⁵¹ Nancy, Jean-Luc, *La décloison (Déconstruction du christianisme, 1)* (Paris: Galilée, 2005), p. 138. See also Nancy, Jean-Luc, *Noli me tangere – Essai sur la levée du corps* (Paris: Bayard, 2003), p. 32ff.

⁵² Blanchot, *Thomas l’obscur*, p. 42.

no longer be distinguished from death, where life «walks» in and as death by means of a step that goes nowhere but toward the repetition of its own aporetic regularity.

Blanchot further explains this aporetic experience through Kafka: “What Kafka gives us”, he observes, “is a sort of combat.” But what does the word «combat» mean here? When describing K., a character in Kafka’s *Castle*, Blanchot tells us that “it does not seem possible that he should die (...). For one thing it isn’t living and dying that are at stake in his combat. But then too he is too tired to die. Too tired for the coming of his death (*l’avènement de sa mort*) not to change into an interminable non arrival (*inavènement interminable*).”⁵³ His combat is an extreme patience, a combat of passivity, the persistence of an ‘interminable non arrival’. This interminable non arrival is death, its immortality,⁵⁴ beyond any form of passage or irreversible transition – death as the abyss of the present, “that toward which I cannot go forth, for in it I do not die”⁵⁵ I forfeit the power of dying. In this abyss «they die»⁵⁶, they never cease to die and they never succeed in dying.

Correlatively to the link that brings together ‘possibility’ and ‘power’, the impossibility that we are trying to consider must be understood in relation to a certain power-lessness: “impossibility – a relation escaping power.”⁵⁷ ‘Escaping’ is to be understood in terms of a refusal of power,⁵⁸ that is, in this precise context, of the capacity of an ego, an ‘I’, to be effective, to actively appropriate its own death. As Marlène Zarader points out in her book on Blanchot, “this would be to insist on a process in the form of mediation: if I take possession of death, if I appropriate it, I can put it at my service, make it work for my own benefit.”⁵⁹ Death becomes ‘possibility’, it is cultivated as the most proper possibility of the individual, as his authentic, *ideal* task: death as the personal act by which the individual deliberately brings about his own end, as the monument of his triumph over the immortality

⁵³ Blanchot, *L’Écriture du Désastre*, p. 214.

⁵⁴ “The immortality of death”, writes Derrida, commenting on Blanchot, “is anything save the eternity of the present. The abidance (*demeurance*) that we will discuss does not remain like the permanence of an eternity. It is time itself.” Derrida, Jacques, *Demeure, Maurice Blanchot* (Paris: Galilée, 1996), p. 89.

⁵⁵ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 160.

⁵⁶ “How different this ‘they’ is from that which we encounter in everyday banality. It is the ‘they’ of impersonal and pre-individual singularities, the ‘they’ of the pure event wherein it dies in the same way that it rains. The splendor of the they is the splendor of the event itself (...).” Deleuze, *Logique du Sens*, p. 178.

⁵⁷ Blanchot, Maurice, *L’Entretien infini* (Paris: Gallimard, 1969), p. 54. This motif of «power-lessness», has been analyzed in detail in Heidegger’s *Besinnung*, the idea of a ‘power-less’ (*Macht-lose*) to be understood beyond power and lack of power, what is outside power and lack of power, and fundamentally unrelated to such. See Heidegger, Martin, *Gesamtausgabe Band 66 – Besinnung* (Frankfurt: Vittorio Klostermann, 1997).

⁵⁸ As John Gregg observes: “<Blanchot> refuses to think of death solely as an instrument of power.” Gregg, John, “Blanchot’s Suicidal Artist: Writing and the (Im)Possibility of Death”. *SubStance*, Vol. 17, No. 1, Issue 55 (1988) p. 48. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3685213>.

⁵⁹ Zarader, Marlène, *L’être et le neutre – à partir de Maurice Blanchot* (Paris: Verdier, 2001), p. 265.

of death. In a radically different manner, Blanchot insists on “the immense passivity of death, which escapes the logic of decisions”, the sovereign position of an ego, death that remains “secret, mysterious, and indecipherable,”⁶⁰ or better, “the neutrality and impersonality in which nothing is accomplished.”⁶¹ The neutral, rightly observes Françoise Proust, “is where everything un-decides itself.”⁶² To die, here, is to take a step back, a radical *renversement* by which death, which “was the extreme form of my power, not only becomes what loosens my hold upon myself (...) but also becomes that which is without any relation to me, without power over me – that which is stripped of all possibility.”⁶³

To make this reversal clearer, we need to return to Blanchot's reading of Rilke. After having sought, in his early work, the kind of authentic death that would fill his historical experience with meaning, Rilke discovered that this path necessarily led to the point where “within myself, I belong to the outside. (...) I am no longer myself (*je ne suis plus moi-même*) (...).”⁶⁴ Blanchot locates this discovery in the pages of *Die Aufzeichnungen des Malte Laurids Brigge*: “Malte’s is the discovery of that force which is too great for us, impersonal death (*la morte impersonnelle*) (...) a discovery that he cannot master.”⁶⁵ Death, impersonal death as a force that cannot be mastered, i.e., by an individual, an ‘I’, death that deprives the individual of the power to say ‘I’, a death in which the individual is but a trace, a vestige⁶⁶, “the impression that will be transformed (*l'impression qui va se métamorphoser*).”⁶⁷ Note, precisely in this sense, the following passage:

<The movement of death> is linked to the infinitude of the metamorphosis which not only leads us to death, but infinitely transmutes death itself, which makes of death the infinite movement of dying

⁶⁰ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 102.

⁶¹ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 113.

⁶² Proust, Françoise, “The Line of Resistance”. *Hypatia: A Journal of Feminist Philosophy*, Vol. 15, No. 4 (2000), p. 26. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3810670>.

⁶³ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 107.

⁶⁴ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 161.

⁶⁵ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 133.

⁶⁶ The image that guides Rilke is that of an anemone: “Flower-muscle that slowly opens back / the anemone to another meadow-dawn, (...). We violent ones (*Gewaltsamen*) remain a little longer. / Ah but *when*, in which of all our lives, / shall we at last be open (*endlich offen*) and receivers?” Rilke, Rainer Maria, *Die Sonette an Orpheus* (Frankfurt am Main: Insel Verlag, 1999), p. 38. As Brent Adkins rightly observes “only in this openness can Rilke begin with death, the nameless, unbidden death that can never be proper to him, that death towards which he can never be.” Adkins, Brent, *Death and desire in Hegel, Heidegger and Deleuze*, p. 203. There is a parallel to be drawn between this ‘flower-muscle’ (*Blumenmuskel*), this open being, without shell or defenses, and the body without organs as Deleuze and Guattari describe it in *L'Anti-Œdipe*, that is as “the model of [impersonal] death.” Deleuze, Gilles, Guattari, Felix, *L'Anti-Œdipe*, p. 393.

⁶⁷ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 133.

and of he who dies he who is infinitely dead, as if in death's intimacy it were for him a matter of dying always more, immeasurably – of continuing inside death to make possible the movement of transformation which must not cease (...).⁶⁸

The movement that death is, insofar as death 'is', in Blanchot's perspective, is to be understood in terms of metamorphosis, of the indefinite survival of metamorphosis, a movement that concerns not only the iterative disruption of any kind of security, configured in terms of identity, of certainty of self, of 'a' self as the foundation of possibility, of meaning, but a permanent injunction of initiality, "where endlessly everything starts over and where dying itself is a task without end (*où sans cesse tout recommence et où mourir même est une tâche sans fin*)."⁶⁹

2. *Film* – the persistence of death

For Deleuze, too, this injunction of initiality constitutes the essence of the problem of death. And death is precisely 'problematic': "(...) the last form of the problematic, the source of problems and questions (...),"⁷⁰ – a impersonal itinerary, Deleuze suggests, "with no relation to 'me', neither present nor past but always coming, the source of an incessant multiple adventure in a persistent question."⁷¹ The element of adventure, the *quaestio* that Deleuze announces, is its persistence: death is 'always coming' (*toujours à venir*). This means not only that death will remain indefinitely perfectible, and thus always insufficient and future, but that, belonging to the time of the promise, it will always remain, in each of its future times, to come. As in Blanchot, death is never present; it remains the theme of a non-presentable concept, and thus is not the term but the interminable, 'always' to come. Deleuze's account of Samuel Beckett's *Film*, provide further elements of analysis regarding this prospective and always insufficient dimension of death. Deleuze deals at length with *Film* in chapter 4 of *Cinéma I - L'Image-Mouvement*, starting with the following question: "How can we rid ourselves of ourselves, and demolish ourselves? This is the astonishing attempt made by Beckett in his cinematographic work entitled '*Film*'. (...) can we escape from 'the happinesses of the *percipere* and

⁶⁸ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 163.

⁶⁹ Blanchot, *L'Espace Littéraire*, p. 164.

⁷⁰ Deleuze, *Différence et répétition*, p. 148.

⁷¹ Deleuze, *Différence et répétition*, p. 148

the *percipi*'? (...)”⁷² Before attempting to illuminate the answer Deleuze might give us, let us try to reconstruct the structure of Beckett’s *Film*.

The work can be divided into three parts. In the first, we see Buster Keaton⁷³, the ‘object’ (O), according to Beckett’s nomenclature⁷⁴, in flight, hurriedly covering a certain spatial extension along a wall, before entering a building and climbing a staircase, always sticking to the edge of the wall. At this stage, the ‘object’ is subject to the following formal convention: the camera, or the ‘eye’ (E), can only film him from the back, from an angle that cannot ever exceed forty-five degrees. When the «eye» exceeds this angle of immunity, the action is immediately suspended; as Beckett writes, the ‘object’ “experiences the anguish of perceivedness”,⁷⁵ interrupting his march and hiding the exposed, threatened part of his face. As a result, the «eye» tries to respect this convention for most of the film.

In the second part, the ‘object’ has entered a room and, insofar as he’s no longer against a wall, the angle of reference of the ‘eye’ doubles (forty-five degrees on each side, thus ninety degrees). The ‘object’ observes the contents of the room subjectively: things, animals. The ‘eye’, on the other hand, objectively perceives, at the same time, the room, the ‘object’ and the elements towards which the ‘object’ projects his gaze. The ‘eye’ cannot yet exceed ninety degrees behind the ‘object’, but the following convention is added: the ‘object’ must empty the room, expel the animals, cover the mirrors and elements that serve as mirrors (windows, frames), tear apart the image of a deity as well as seven photograph’s that represent him in different stages of his life. This exercise aims to extinguish the ‘object’s’ point of view, to eliminate the subjective perception. Only the objective perception of the ‘eye’ should remain. At this point, the ‘object’ can finally install himself in the rocking chair in the center of the room, rocking gently with his eyes closed.⁷⁶

⁷² Deleuze, Gilles, *Cinéma 1 – L’Image-Mouvement* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1983), p. 97.

⁷³ In *Le plus grand film irlandais (Film, de Beckett)*, Deleuze affirms, without explanation, that the role “could only have been played by Buster Keaton.” See Deleuze, Gilles – *Critique et Clinique* (Paris: Les Éditions du Minuit, 1993), p. 36. The casting of Keaton was not at all inevitable, however, he was, in fact, not even the second or third choice for the role, but the fourth choice, after Chaplin, Zero Mostel and Jackie MacGowran. See Ardoin, Paul, “Beckett’s film, “which could only have been played by Buster Keaton” (2015), *Angelaki*, 20: 4, pp. 5-21. DOI: 10.1080/0969725X.2015.1096627

⁷⁴ See Beckett’s screenplay in Beckett, Samuel, “Film”. In *The Complete Dramatic Works* (London: Faber and Faber, 2006), pp. 319-332.

⁷⁵ Beckett, *Film*, p. 321.

⁷⁶ “All that remains is the Rocking Chair in the center of the room, because, more than any bed, it is the sole piece of furniture that exists before or after man, that which suspends us in the middle of nothingness (to-and-fro).” Deleuze, *Critique et Clinique*, p. 38.

In the third and final stage of the film the greatest danger is revealed: the extinction of the subjective perception of the ‘object’ has freed the ‘eye’ from all conventions that limit its movement. The ‘eye’ then advances carefully through the available space, into the domain of the remaining two hundred and seventy degrees. At times, the ‘object’ wakes and, regaining “a scrap of subjective perception”,⁷⁷ hides, curls up and forces the ‘eye’ to fall back. Finally, taking advantage of the ‘object’s’ torpor, the ‘eye’ succeeds in coming round and facing him. The ‘object’ is now seen from the front, and the last convention is unveiled: “the pursuing perceiver”, writes Beckett, “is not extraneous, but self.”⁷⁸ We are in the domain, Deleuze suggests, “of the perception of affection, the most terrifying, that which still survives when all the others have been destroyed: it is the perception of self by self, (*la perception de soi par soi*).”⁷⁹ Face-to-face with himself the «object» realizes that it is impossible not to be seen.⁸⁰ To use a formula from Beckett’s *Worstward ho*, “in the skull all save the skull gone.”⁸¹ The perception of the self, self-perception, however, leads not to identification, but to disquiet, uncanniness. What is uncanny is unfamiliar, beyond our ken, and thus unsettling, dis-quieting. The self is no less foreign, no less strange, than all the other selves. *Film* concerns a pursuit, the vicissitudes of a pursuit, not just any pursuit, between different subjects, but a pursuit of the self by the self, the self-pursuit of a self that wants to identify itself, to fully conceive itself as such, but that does not exist, after all, beyond the fracture that makes it perpetually differ from himself. As Tomás Maia rightfully suggests, *Film* must be understood in terms of a quest; “it accomplishes what may be called the human *quaestio* (the quest) – a quest with no other object than the unobjectifiable openness of the one who pursues (*a abertura inobjetivável daquele que busca*).”⁸² Therefore at the end of the pursuit, of every *quaestio* worthy of the name, there is no revealable self, no *ideal* anteriority that could fill with meaning the endeavor undertaken, no end of the pursuit.

This is precisely what *Film*'s end sequence gives us to see, to think about: first, the ‘object’ bowed forward, his head in his hands, gently rocking; then a clear cut to a black screen; finally, the lift of an eyelid, an open eye, the same image we saw at the beginning of the film, the open eye that inaugurated the pursuit, the *quaestio*. And so, at the end of the pursuit, of the quest, nothing but to remain in

⁷⁷ Deleuze, *Cinéma 1*, p. 98.

⁷⁸ Beckett, *Film*, p. 321.

⁷⁹ Deleuze, *Cinéma 1*, p. 99.

⁸⁰ “Search of non-being in flight from extraneous perception breaking down in inescapability of self-perception.” Beckett, *Film*, p. 321.

⁸¹ Beckett, Samuel, *Nohow on. Company, Ill Seen Ill Said, Worstward ho* (London: John Calder 1989), p. 114.

⁸² Maia, Tomás, *O Olho Divino – Beckett e o cinema* (Lisboa: Documenta, 2016), p. 37.

pursuit, in question, to ‘fail again’. A pursuit for nothing. Beckett’s *Film* invites us to understand cinema – what there is of cinema, of movement, in cinema – in terms of suspense, of an unlimited postponement:⁸³ the character exposition⁸⁴ before his nothingness, each time the impossibility of identifying himself, his own self, and to finally being able to die an authentic, proper death. “Death,” writes Tomás Maia, “bleeds, but does not die – that is all that art gives us to see and, probably, to know. Death inspires, but itself, does not expire.”⁸⁵

The figure of the exhausted person, Deleuze’s argues in *L’Épuisé*, expresses the fundamental aspect of Beckett’s characters. Exhaustion, however, must not be confused with simple tiredness: “The tired person (*le fatigué*) no longer has any (subjective) possibility at his disposal; he therefore cannot realize the slightest (objective) possibility. But the latter remains, because one can never realize the whole of the possible.”⁸⁶ The tired person only has exhausted realization. The exhausted person, in turn, exhausts the whole of the possible, he can no longer possibilize. He exhausts himself in exhausting the possible: “He has had done with the possible, beyond all tiredness, ‘for to end yet again’ (*pour en finir encore*).”⁸⁷ What is affected here, exhausted, precisely, is the idea of a simple and unmodified, indifferent origin that is always already at work every time we enter the domain of the ‘possible’, that is as the possible of a merely represented *possibilitas*, the *essentia* of an *actus of existentia*: “God is the originary”, writes Deleuze, “the ensemble of all possibility.”⁸⁸ The possible is thus a question of derivation, of consequence, we realize the possible according to certain capabilities and certain finalities, projects, and preferences that vary fundamentally, forever excluding or replacing the preceding ones. This series of exclusions, these substitutions, produce, precisely, fatigue, tiredness. ‘Exhaustion’ proceeds in an entirely different way: “one combines the set of

⁸³ This is something – a process, a movement – that Beckett himself had already discerned and admired in the painting of the Van Velde Brothers, ‘Peintres de l’empêchement’: “An endless unveiling, veil after veil, plane after plane of imperfect transparencies, an unveiling towards the *indévoilable*, the nothing, the thing again (*le rien, la chose à nouveau*).” Beckett, Samuel, *Le monde et le pantalon* (Paris: Editions de Minuit, 1990), p. 58.

⁸⁴ I understand the notion of ‘exposition’ in the terms established by Jean-Luc Nancy: “‘Exposition’ doesn’t mean that intimacy is extracted from its withdrawal and carried outside, put on display, because then the body would be an exposition of the ‘self’, in the sense of a translation, an interpretation, or a staging. «Exposition», on the contrary, means that expression itself is an intimacy and a withdrawal. The *a-part-self* is not translated or incarnated into exposition; it is what it is there: this vertiginous withdrawal of the self from the self that is needed to open the infinity of that withdrawal *all the way up to* self. The body is this departure of self to self.” Nancy, Jean-Luc, *Corpus* (Paris: Éditions Métailié, 2000), p. 32.

⁸⁵ Maia, *O Olho Divino – Beckett e o cinema*, pp. 32-33.

⁸⁶ Deleuze, Gilles, “L’Épuisé”. In Samuel Beckett, et Gilles Deleuze, *Quad et autres pièces pour la télévision, suivi de L’Épuisé, par Gilles Deleuze* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 1992), p. 57

⁸⁷ Deleuze, *L’Épuisé*, p. 58. See also Beckett, Samuel, *For to end yet again and other Fizzles* (London: John Calder, 1976).

⁸⁸ Deleuze, *L’Épuisé*, p. 58

variables of a situation, on the condition that one renounce any order of preference, any organization in relation to a goal, any signification.”⁸⁹ This is not to say that the exhausted person inhabits or is inhabited by a fundamental indifference or passivity: “one does not fall into the undifferentiated,” Deleuze observes, “nor is one passive.”⁹⁰ The exhausted person activates himself, but for nothing, in a world freed, in Nietzsche’s words, “from servitude under purpose (*der Knechtschaft unter dem Zwecke*)”.⁹¹ This ‘freedom’ is entirely relative to the withdrawal of an I, a self, in and as the immovable foundation of a succession of variable preferences. As Asja Szafraniec rightly observes, following Deleuze: “the reverse, correlated side of the project of exhausting the possible is the exhausting of the self that performs the exhausting. Exhausting the possible is thus coextensive with exhausting oneself.”⁹² Beckett’s characters are precisely this withdrawal, the endless exhaustion of the onto-theo-logical place of the self, its interminable death.

This ‘interminable death’, as we saw in *Film*, or rather, as Beckett *shows us* in *Film*, is echoed by an ‘interminable life’, but here the word ‘life’, in Blanchot’s terms, signifies “the loss of the power to die, the loss of death as power and possibility.”⁹³ Blanchot addresses the nature of Beckett’s characters in *Le Livre à venir*: we must consider “a nameless being (...) a being without being who can neither live nor die, cannot cease or begin, (...) with a perseverance that does not indicate any power but rather the curse of what cannot be interrupted (...).”⁹⁴ Neither live nor die, the perseverance of an in-between, without subordination. What perseveres, what remains between life and death is *life death* as an inseparable constellation, beyond any antinomic regime, any adequate delimitation. Deleuze, precisely in this regard, is interested in a certain ‘involution’: “To involute is to be ‘between’ (*Involuer, c’est être ‘entre’*), in the middle, adjacent. Beckett’s characters are in perpetual involution, always in the middle of a path, already *en route*.”⁹⁵ Perpetually *en route*, on the way to nothing, for

⁸⁹ Deleuze, *L’Épuisé*, p. 59. For a further exploration of the Deleuzian concept of ‘exhaustion’ see Szafraniec, Asja, Beckett’s “Exhausted” Archives. In *Beckett, Derrida, and the Event of Literature* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2007), pp. 98-117; Wasser, Audrey. “A Relentless Spinozism: Deleuze’s Encounter with Beckett.” *SubStance* 41, no. 1 (2012): 124–36. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23261107>; Nabais, Catarina Pombo, Troisième Chapitre – Beckett et l’épuisement du possible, In *Gilles Deleuze: philosophie et littérature* (Paris: L’Harmattan, 2013) pp. 409-441; Wisniowska, Magdalena. “Deleuze and Beckett: An Immanent Encounter.” *Deleuze Studies* 8, no. 2 (2014): 173–98. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/45331798>. Agamben, Giorgio, Posture. In Deleuze, Gilles, *L’Esausto* (Firenze: Nottetempo, 2015).

⁹⁰ Deleuze, *L’Épuisé*, p. 59.

⁹¹ Nietzsche, *Sämtliche Werke Band 4 – Also sprach Zarathustra I–IV*, p. 209.

⁹² Szafraniec, *Beckett, Derrida, and the Event of Literature*, p. 99.

⁹³ Blanchot, *L’Espace Littéraire*, p. 254.

⁹⁴ Blanchot, Maurice, *Le Livre à Venir* (Paris: Gallimard, 1959), p. 290.

⁹⁵ Deleuze, Gilles; Parnet, Claire, *Dialogues* (Paris: Flammarion, 1996), p. 38.

nothing – and if this is, as Deleuze also reminds us, a matter of “attaining once more (*rejoindre*) the world before man, before our own dawn,” to ascend “towards the luminous plane of immanence, the plane of matter and its cosmic eddying of movement-images,”⁹⁶ then this ‘attaining once more’, this *rejoinder*, must be carefully understood. It is not, as the philosopher explains in Section 10 of *Mille Plateaux*, “a regression leading back to a principle. It is on the contrary an involution, in which form is constantly being dissolved (*où la forme ne cesse pas d'être dissoute*) (...).”⁹⁷ The movement that Deleuze wants us to consider does not lead to a principle, does not cease to dissolve its very possibility, its consistency, stability, and identifiable collectedness in a ‘form’. To *Rejoindre* is, precisely, to constantly involute. The emphasis must be placed on the adverbial phrase: ‘ne cesse pas’, a form is *constantly* being dissolved. Deleuze’s answer to the question “How can we rid ourselves of ourselves, and demolish ourselves?”, that is, how can we go from the world of experiences, perceptions, affects and actions back to immanence, is, essentially, negative: we can’t. After all, “nothing is ever finished in Beckett, nothing ever dies (*rien ne finit chez Beckett, rien ne meurt*).”⁹⁸ Above all death. The experience that no one experiences, the experience of death, “occurs in life and for life, in every passage or becoming, in every intensity as passage or becoming. (...) death is what is felt in every feeling, *what never ceases and never finishes happening in every becoming (ce qui ne cesse pas et ne finit pas d'arriver dans tout devenir)*.”⁹⁹

The last essay Deleuze ever wrote, *L'Immanence: une vie...*, further explores this aporetic persistence of ‘life death’:

What is immanence? A life... No one has described what *a life* is better than Charles Dickens, when he takes the indefinite article as an index of the transcendental. A scoundrel, a bad apple, held in contempt by everyone, is found on the point of death (*mourant*), and suddenly those charged with his care display an urgency, respect, and even love for the dying man's least sign of life. Everyone makes it his business to save him. As a result, the wicked man himself in the depths of his coma, feels something soft and sweet penetrate his soul. But as he progresses back toward life. his benefactors turn cold, and he himself rediscovers his old vulgarity and meanness. Between his life and his death, there is a moment where *a life* is merely playing with death. The life of the individual has given way to an impersonal and yet singular life which foregrounds a pure event that has been liberated from

⁹⁶ Deleuze, *Cinéma 1*, p. 100.

⁹⁷ Deleuze, Gilles, Guattari, Felix, *Mille Plateaux. Capitalisme et schizophrénie 2*, p. 326.

⁹⁸ Deleuze, *Critique et Clinique*, p. 38.

⁹⁹ Deleuze, Guattari, *L'Anti-Œdipe - Capitalisme et schizophrénie*, p. 394

the accidents of internal and external life, that is, from the subjectivity and the objectivity of what comes to pass.¹⁰⁰

What is described here is the space between life and death, the very in-between between life and death, *le mourant*, his undying death as impersonal life, irreducible to accidents, lived experiences, states of affairs, to the ego-cratic apparatus of a subject, a self. What interests Deleuze, as we have seen at length, is not death, definitive death as agency toward a definitive transition, but its impossibility, the impossibility of death, of the end's ending: life as the *encounter* of death with death, that is, in Deleuze's words, "the point at which death turns against death; where dying is the destitution of death, (...) and also the figure which the most singular life takes on in order to substitute itself for me."¹⁰¹

Coda – *Death's resurrection*

Beckett's characters, Deleuze suggests, 'are in perpetual involution', i.e., not in a process toward totalization but always dissolving its very possibility. The problem must be considered in terms of 'becoming': "in becoming it is a matter of involuting; it's neither regression nor progression. To become is to become more and more restrained, more and more simple, more and more deserted and for that very reason populated."¹⁰² The emphasis should be on simplicity, that is, undoing any form of crystallization, everything that roots each of us in ourselves, in our molarity."¹⁰³ Involution is this moving away from molarity, this *decrecendo*, or even *moriendo*¹⁰⁴. But this *moriendo*, as Jean-Luc Nancy made clear, "is not finishing; it is unfinished (*infinissant*),"¹⁰⁵ to finish yet again, and still to die. This is 'the immense passivity of death' that Blanchot talked about, the neutrality and impersonality in which nothing is accomplished, where everything un-decides itself. 'Passivity' to be understood, without paradox, in an active way, i.e., in terms of persistence, the assertion of a duration

¹⁰⁰ Deleuze, Gilles, *Deux régimes de fous textes et entretiens, 1975-1995* (Paris: Les Éditions de Minuit, 2003), p. 361.

¹⁰¹ Deleuze, *Logique du Sens*, p. 179 Note the symmetry between this passage from 1969 and that of *L'Immanence: une vie* quoted above, written 26 years later, in 1995, shortly before Deleuze's death.

¹⁰² Deleuze, *Dialogues*, p. 37.

¹⁰³ Deleuze, *Mille Plateaux. Capitalisme et schizophrénie 2*, pp. 342-343.

¹⁰⁴ I am thinking, of course, of the book to which Roger Laporte gave that title. See Laporte, Roger, *Moriendo* (Paris: P.O.L., 1983).

¹⁰⁵ Nancy, Jean-Luc, *À l'écoute* (Paris : Gallée, 2002), p. 52.

that lasts: dying as “the incessant imminence whereby life lasts, desiring. The imminence of what has always already come to pass.”¹⁰⁶

One of Deleuze's most significant and, to our knowledge, most neglected contributions to this debate¹⁰⁷ is the claim that cinema is consubstantial to death, is ‘the point at which death turns against death’, and that is only to the degree that it is engaged in resurrection and does nothing but espouse its movement. What is this movement? What does ‘resurrection’ mean here? Retracing its role in Deleuze's work is, of course, an endeavor that deserves an entire essay of its own. As a preliminary remark, allow me merely to note that ‘resurrection’ is a rare but decisive concept in Deleuze’s works on cinema. In *Cinéma 1*, for instance, we read the following: “to the eternal return as reproduction of something always already accomplished, is opposed the eternal return as resurrection (*l'éternel retour comme résurrection*), a new gift of the new (...).”¹⁰⁸ This idea is taken up again in *Cinéma 2*, with a quotation from Artaud's *La Coquille et le clergyman*: “We are not copying Artaud, but Artaud lived and said something about the brain that concerns all of us: that «its antennae turned towards the invisible», that it has a capacity to «resume a resurrection of death» (*recommencer une résurrection de la mort*).”¹⁰⁹

Although these two passages certainly require further investigation, they allow us to state the following: resurrection is not, here, a miraculous story, nor its Lazarus the agent of a prodigious operation, as in the Gospel of John¹¹⁰, he who goes into death to pass through it, to transgress it by regaining his life, effecting a resurrection that dialecticizes death, making it a necessary stage in the service of the constitution of meaning, of an onto-theo-logical program. There is another Lazarus at play in cinema,¹¹¹ “the only true Lazarus, whose very death was resurrected (*dont la mort même était*

¹⁰⁶ Blanchot, *L'Écriture du Désastre*, p. 70 See Derrida's reading of this passage in Derrida, Jacques – *Demeure: Maurice Blanchot*, pp. 59ff.

¹⁰⁷ There is an important exception: Viegas, Susana, “Death as Film-Philosophy's Muse - Deleuzian Observations on Moving Images and the Nature of Time”, *Film-Philosophy* 27.2 (2023): P. 222-239. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3366/film.2023.0227>

¹⁰⁸ Deleuze, *Cinéma 1 – L'Image-Mouvement*, p. 185.

¹⁰⁹ Deleuze, *Cinéma 2 – L'Image-Temps*, pp. 275-276.

¹¹⁰ Nor the Messiah who resurrects him, the one who says, ‘I am resurrection’ (Ἐγώ εἰμι ἡ ἀνάστασις) (John 11, 25). The immortality of Jesus does not mean that, crucified, he did not die; on the contrary, it means that it is precisely insofar as he died on the cross that he is immortal: he overcame death by dying, and thus entered the realm of eternal life, that is, to use the formula of St. John of the Cross, where ‘I live because I do not die’. The impossibility of dying is, in this case, a victory over death, the affirmation of an all-powerful principle capable of giving life to the dead. It is an entirely different problem that we are trying to pose here: resurrection is not eternal life but an infinite dying.

¹¹¹ I am not sure, however, that this allows us to speak of cinema, to use Jean Cayrol's concept, in terms of ‘Lazarean art’ (*art lazaréen*), as it does for Griselda Pollock and Max Silverman, editors of the collective work

ressuscitée).”¹¹² Death is the subject: the subject is not, or is no longer, its own subject. As Jean-Luc Nancy explains, “such are the stakes of resurrection: neither subjectivation nor objectivation. Neither ‘the resurrected’ nor the dead body – but ‘death resurrected’”¹¹³, the ever-returning event of its persistence beyond any kind of suspension: “and the event is that no one ever dies, but has always just died and is always going to die (*vient toujours de mourir et va toujours mourir*).”¹¹⁴

Concentrationary Art: Jean Cayrol, the Lazarean and the Everyday in Post-war Film, Literature, Music and the Visual Arts, that is to understand Lazarus as an ‘emblematic figure’, a ‘symbol of the new art’, a ‘model’, a ‘prototype’. The Lazarus we are trying to consider does not have the stability, the consistency of a model; rather, he is the disruption of the very possibility of a model, of a previous figure. See also Pollock, Griselda, Silverman, Max (eds.), *Concentrationary cinema: Aesthetics as political resistance in Alain Resnais's Night and Fog* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2011).

¹¹² Blanchot, *Thomas l'obscur*, p. 42.

¹¹³ Nancy, *La décloison*, p. 138.

¹¹⁴ Deleuze, *Logique du Sens*, p. 80.

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